

Effects of Video Recording Platform (Flipgrid) on English as Second Language Students' Oral Performance

Clark Vincent D. Bayotas

Liceo De Cagayan University, Cagayan De Oro City, Philippines

Suggested Citation

Bayotas, C.V.D. (2023). Effects of Video Recording Platform (Flipgrid) on English as Second Language Students' Oral Performance. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 857-873.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).72](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).72)

Abstract:

This study is a quasi-experimental method of research that employed the pretest-posttest-control group design. This aimed to determine the effects of using Flipgrid, a video recording platform, on the oral performance of 80 ESL learners of the Junior High School Department of Liceo de Cagayan University. Forty participants were classified as the experimental group, exposed to speaking tasks using Flipgrid. The other forty were classified as the control group, where they did conventional speaking tasks using Google Meet. In order to gather the data needed, the speaking module of IELTS was modified as a pretest and posttest and was administered before and after the

intervention. As for the rating scale, the public version of the IELTS speaking rubric was adopted. The findings revealed that both groups exposed to Flipgrid and conventional speaking tasks significantly increased their oral performance after the intervention. It was concluded that Flipgrid can improve students' oral language performance. Moreover, it was recommended that future researchers conduct studies on Flipgrid during limited face-to-face classes and adopt both conventional and video-recording speaking tasks.

Keywords: *Flipgrid, google meet, video recording speaking tasks, conventional speaking tasks, oral performance.*

Introduction

The critical role of English as a means of global communication is not deniable. To be competent in English, learners need to master all four skills, namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Among these four skills, speaking is the foremost skill that bridges students to the world (Leong & Ahmadi, 2016). In other words, improving oral performance is extremely necessary for students since it assists them in growing needs in a changing world. However, it is difficult and demanding for EFL learners to talk in English (Arifin, 2017; Fauzan, 2016; Leong & Ahmadi, 2016). Even after spending years studying English, some students still

struggle to communicate clearly and spontaneously (Bueno et al., 2013).

Similar situations can be found in the Philippine context. Although the Philippines is still one of the preferred countries for foreign learners of English due to the affordability and quality of its English as Second Language Programs being offered, there is a worrying trend of decreasing the English competence of learners. The English proficiency of the Filipino workforce has declined (EF et al., 2016), which might be attributed to Filipino graduates having only English proficiency at the primary working proficiency level.

Numerous and varied studies have been conducted to determine the factors that affect

English proficiency, particularly the language learning of non-native English users. Among the reasons for those mentioned above, precisely, one potential aspect that influences learners' oral performance is anxiety (Belegdair, 2015). There is evidence that language anxiety incapacitates the language learner and is one of the best indicators of language learning performance. While encouraging anxiety improves students' performance, excessive anxiety might have the opposite impact.

In order to help ESL high school learners reduce their anxiety in speaking and increase their motivation to study English speaking, applying ICT in the classrooms is one of the appropriate ways. Learning using technology will academically progress if used wisely and successfully (Sharma et al., 2012). The internet, computers, digital cameras, mobile phones, programs, and other tools can all assist teachers and students in achieving their learning goals in this regard.

In terms of educational applications, Flipgrid is practical to help students manage anxiety while learning to speak English and hone their speaking abilities. Flipgrid is simple to use and suitable for teaching speaking, according to Lamb (2015), who claimed it may be used to teach languages. This application is relevant to learners who need more time to practice speaking inside or outside the classroom in their learning routines. It is also possible for those who fear making mistakes, shyness, and lack confidence when speaking English in front of the class (Tan, 2019).

However, although several studies have explored the utilization of Flipgrid and other digital video recording platforms in foreign language speaking classes as a way of increasing learners' exposure to the target language, the majority of these studies either only focused on learners' perceptions of the incorporation of the platform into speaking classes, or were conducted in an ESL context, where learners might have had many other opportunities to practice the target language. Additionally, very little, if any, study has been done on the relative impact of video

recordings on learners' spoken language performance.

These reasons are the foundation for the current study, which aims to evaluate the impact of utilizing Flipgrid to video record speaking activities on the oral language proficiency of ESL students.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the effects of using Flipgrid on the oral performance of ESL learners of the Junior High School Department of Liceo de Cagayan University. In this context, the study specifically sought to accomplish the following objectives:

1. What is the level of oral performance of the students exposed to conventional English speaking tasks using Google Meet during the pretest and posttest exams;
2. What is the level of oral performance of the students exposed to video recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid during the pretest and posttest exams; and
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of oral performance between students who are exposed to conventional speaking tasks using Google Meet and video recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid?

Literature Review

This chapter presents the review of related literature and studies, foreign and local, relevant to the present study. Presented in this section are the concepts, theories, and previous studies on virtual learning's impact on ESL students' learning outcomes.

Conventional Speaking Tasks using Google Meet

As a consequence of the ongoing pandemic, schools have moved entirely toward dispersed, virtual, and distant learning environments (Harris, 2020). In 21st century education, great interest has been devoted to practical means for reflecting on comprehensive education curriculum frameworks (Pittman, 2021).

Many tools, like Zoom, Google Meet, and others, are currently available for free access to facilitate effective learning and may be used to learn spoken English. In addition, Google Meet is a program or application that may be utilized to continue working productively even if you do so from home. Between January and March 2020, the number of daily users of the Google Meet app climbed by a factor of 25. Numerous studies demonstrate how difficult it is to learn how to speak English.

This research work seeks to spotlight Google Meet technology as a new wave of online education especially in conducting conventional speaking tasks in an ESL class. There is a common requirement for GM as a digital online platform for language learning through which teachers and students can meet each other in an academic framework (David, 2018; Chandra, 2020; Lander, 2014). Several recent studies have pointed out that synchronous learning enables learners to partake in the learning process (David, 2018; Chandra, 2020). It is significant for language teachers to use Google Meet to structure, post, and save lectures on the platforms. Effectual planning develops effective execution and generates opportunities for ultimate objects of classes (Melissa, 2020 and Salvador, 2019).

Previous studies have underlined prevalent formats for synchronous learning, which might comprise traditional classroom sessions, web-based classes, and live streaming sessions exploiting social media networks (Moore and Kearsley, 2012). Mainly, it is well acknowledged in prior studies that there are many benefits to using social media networks in an asynchronous mode for online distance education schedules, even if numerous remind that there are drawbacks Landar (2014) Davis (2018) & Chandra (2020).

Mishra (2020) employed a survey (among 260 students and 78 teachers) to spotlight online teaching tools, and the approaches used at Mizoram University of India. The results disclosed that teachers and students utilized WhatsApp/ Instagram and Email. The findings reveal that participants were inclined to use

network applications to give assignments and to provide feedback. Forty-five percent of teachers used Zoom, Google Meet, Cisco WebEx, and Skype platforms to carry out online classes, whereas 32% of teachers were utilizing Google classroom. However, the study reported that 15% of students unload the learning materials.

Many advocates of digital education prop up that to yield effectiveness and efficiency in online learning, some digital competencies are strongly required (Emon, Alif, & Islam., 2020). It is said that it is pricey because the plugins used in these platforms must be paid for. Then again, an internet connection is a prerequisite to gaining access to online lectures and downloading learning material (Afrianto, 2016 and Lee, 2018).

Nevertheless, there is a significant number of studies on the advantages of synchronous online learning mode as it develops an enhanced platform for a feedback loop ,enabling learners to share prospects and feedback instantly (Statt, 2017; Davis,2018; Hammoodi,2020., Bordoloi et al.,2021). It was stated, in the literature, that this makes a facilitating setting for feedback from teachers and students, enabling them to rectify their mistakes and receive positive feedback from the virtual social group (Thomson, 2017). Lewandoski (2015) concluded that online learning promotes the perception of teamwork, more willingly than individual work. Different studies unearth that learners prefer to learn more online than on-site primarily when exploring the two learning environments (David, 2018; Chinaza, 2021). Melissa, 2020 and Statt(2017)believed that merging the two learning environments would be an extra chance for those who missed the live sessions, as they can see the classroom videos afterward.

Conversely, Huber (2020) states that students were not motivated to learn distantly during the lockdown. Also, a study in Malaysia uncovered that, during school closure, students' engagement and learning attainment were reduced in the online learning approaches (Tan, 2021).

A recent study claims that there is an imbalanced facility in terms of decisions and procedures to manage the learning failures, resulting from

school closure (Lorente & Pulido-Montes, 2020). A study by Adnan and Anwar (2020) disclosed that, in underdeveloped countries, most students could not access the internet because of technological and financial difficulties; online learning cannot reach the wanted results. Moreover, university students complained about a lack of interaction with teachers, and inadequate classroom socialization (Nursat, 2021).

Conversely, Lorente, et al. (2020) stated that it is crucial to communicate rational educational policies that support government response facilities, primarily in developing countries. Though plenty of research has been done, appropriate strategies and adequate conditions still require investigations, mostly in underdeveloped countries. Besides, limited internet connection, shortage of access points, and pricey data packages were the major restraints of online education in developing countries (Pittman, 2021).

It is highly critical for teachers and students to acquire digital competencies (Huber & Helm, 2020). Also, teaching aptitudes should be underpinned (Tria, 2020). Findings of Shehzadi's study (2020) confirmed that students' abilities to retain information might be reinforced when having the learning materials saved on the network platforms.

Previous research has been done by Zaenal (2020), Juniartini (2020), as well as Dewi, Tuisda, and Putra (2021). The first focuses on utilizing Google Meet to do remote work in the wake of the 2019 pandemic of Coronavirus disease (Covid-19) (Zenal, 2020). The conclusion is that Google Meet is a program that can be utilized to continue working productively even when users work from home. In addition, according to Juniartini (2020), Google Meet enables users to conduct remote interviews, virtual training sessions, teaching and learning activities, and much more. A research by Dewi, Tuisda, and Putra (2021) also demonstrates how the Google Meet Application may facilitate teaching and learn for both teachers and students.

According to the findings of the earlier research, Google Meet is among the top options for

addressing the need for English language instruction in the context of the Covid-19 epidemic. The prior research, however, did not reveal how the students perceived speaking competence on the Google Meet platform or how they perceived speaking talent that was engaging. By investigating the issue of "Engaging students speaking skill utilizing google meet platform: Students perspective," this study aims to close the gap.

Video Recording Speaking Tasks Using Flipgrid

Many techniques are suggested to increase the speaking skill among students. One of them is self-video recording. Self-recording is making an automatic record. Students need to develop fluency and confidence in their oral language through experiences in many types of speech situations. They can convey their thought, information, and feeling through oral communication Widiyawati (2014).

Among the popular educational self-recording video applications is Flipgrid. Flipgrid is a free online video discussion platform from Microsoft that aids teachers see and listening to every student in the class and creating an enjoyable and supportive social learning environment (Flipgrid, 2020). Lecturers submit conversation starters on Flipgrid, and students respond with little films. Students get the chance to engage face-to-face online thanks to Flipgrid. This also facilitates students to do virtual classroom discussion that enables them to interact with the other virtual class members. The use of Flipgrid as an online video discussion platform could provide students with an opportunity to share their speaking performances freely and confidently. The implementation of Flipgrid is expected to be an innovative solution for integrating the technological-based teaching model in English as a second language class.

Flipgrid increases students' perception of a natural interaction by showing different social features that represent a conversation (Clark et al., 2015). Therefore, other researchers present Flipgrid as a video discussion board where students can record their videos and interact with their classmates to improve their speaking

skills (Green & Green, 2018). In Flipgrid, teachers create a topic and students upload short video responses using a custom link. This makes this an easy tool to work with students during class or as home tasks (Stoszkowski, 2018).

In addition, Fahey et al. (2019) reports that using Flipgrid is not about recording videos. It is about learning that is social and personal. It can happen anywhere and anytime, and it is about making connections. Flipgrid also offers deep exploration and endorses that everyone can be a teacher and a learner as well. The use of Flipgrid can create an EFL learning atmosphere that makes students enjoy the class. To some extent, Flipgrid enables students who are not really confident in expressing their ideas in face-to-face interaction to perform really well in responding to the topic of Flipgrid discussion. They might perform expressively when they record themselves on the grid discussion.

Several types of research have been carried out to gain a better understanding of Flipgrid's contributions to online learning. One of the earliest published studies that examine the efficacy of using Flipgrid in a language teaching context is McLain (2018) who found Flipgrid to be an effective learning tool for Business English Writing students in Korea. Student participants in McLain's study reported that Flipgrid was beneficial for them to engage in language practice from home. Many participants also reported that they had perceived an increase in their English-speaking ability. Tuyet and Khang (2020) studied the effects of the anxiety that Flipgrid had on their EFL students in Vietnam. They found that Flipgrid had a positive effect on reducing stress and anxiety when speaking English among many of their students.

The most notable research related to this study is that of Mango (2021) used Flipgrid with 30 students enrolled in the Arabic as a World Language (AWL) course in America. The purpose of Mango's study was to investigate his students' attitudes and perceptions of the use of Flipgrid including its advantages and disadvantages. Mango found that 53% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that Flipgrid helped them develop their speaking and

listening skills and confidence in public speaking. Mango also conducted qualitative research using an open-ended questionnaire asking what students thought were the advantages and disadvantages of using Flipgrid for speaking activities and found that respondents rated Flipgrid positively because it provided a stress-free environment for speaking and listening and it allowed the tracking of language progress. These two themes made up about 75% of responses, and the third theme which made up about 25% of responses, the use of Flipgrid built confidence in speaking and listening skills.

With the features such as real-time video chatting and video discussions, Flipgrid is proven to effectively promote collaborative learning and learning engagement (Agan et al., 2019; Innes, 2020; Johnson & Skarphol, 2018; McLain, 2018; Miller et al., 2020; Stoszkowski et al., 2020). Students have an opportunity to present videos on a discussion grid, watch peers' videos and receive feedback from teachers, which creates connections among peers and teachers. Furthermore, it is believed that Flipgrid opens up more learning environments to students so that they can practice their speaking skills ubiquitously on various topics and elongate their speaking time (McLain, 2018).

A study conducted by Syahrizal and Pamungkas (2020) shows that students' verbal language fluency increased with a decrease in pauses when speaking the target language. Students became more autonomous and independent when using the English language orally through Flipgrid. Moreover, Amirulloh et al. (2020) stated that students' fluency, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and vocabulary improved while using Flipgrid.

With regard to speaking ability, Forsythe and Raine (2019) reveal that Flipgrid could boost students' confidence in speaking performances. Recently, Lowenthal and Moore (2020) argue that when recording videos, students will learn to structure their ideas in a way that they can contentedly present them. Even those who are not very confident, are still able to post a video with an icon or a funny emoji as their avatars;

therefore, Flipgrid helps cultivate not only creativity but also flexibility.

Tuyet and Khang (2020) also explored the usage of Flipgrid to assist ESL high school students in reducing their anxiety about learning English and evaluating the learners' opinions toward its applications in a study. The study used a mixed method and a quasi-experimental approach with 60 EFL tenth-grade students in the Mekong Delta. The modified Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), interviews, and questionnaires were employed as research instruments in this study. The results showed that after learning Flipgrid, EFL high school students' anxiety levels in learning English speaking decreased. Furthermore, the majority of students indicated enthusiasm for the usage of Flipgrid in English-language learning. Flipgrid was expected to be used frequently to make English-language instruction more entertaining.

The results indicate that the Flipgrid program has a good impact on students' interests, English speaking improvement, and confidence. This result is supported by data from a separate study conducted with 60 tenth-grade students at a high school in the Mekong Delta, which found that students have positive attitudes and preferences toward using Flipgrid to support their speaking lessons (Tuyet & Khang, 2020). Specifically, the adoption of the Flipgrid app is reported to reduce tenth-grade students' anxiety in speaking practice. More importantly, the findings highlight that when acquiring speaking skills, the Flipgrid app could strengthen collaborative learning skills, autonomous learning ability, and reflective learning.

Another study undertaken by Keiper, White, Carlson, and Lupinek (2020) is a mixed strategy, an exploratory study aiming to determine the usefulness of the Flipgrid. Using Flipgrid, a mobile video community forum learning resource, is possible in HyFlex business programs. The study was conducted with 10 undergraduate and graduate business education classes using a set of questionnaires that included both Likert-style and open-ended items. Flipgrid is a useful learning platform, according to the findings, and students found it to be both

beneficial and helpful. Flipgrid is a useful tool for online learning, according to various research. Using Flipgrid to promote discussion around the community is a good idea, and it can help students improve their speaking time, pronunciation, and teamwork. Few studies have looked at the use of Flipgrid to boost students' speaking skills, especially in the context of EFL. The majority of research on Flipgrid was mainly on how students saw it and how it affected their motivation. The goal of this study is to determine whether using Flipgrid's features may help students' speaking skills.

Oral Language Performance

Humans are programmed to speak before they learn to read and write. In any given, human beings spend much more time interacting orally with language rather than using it in its written form. Speaking is the most important skill because it is one of the abilities that is needed to perform a conversation. English speaking is not an easy task because speakers should know many significant components like pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. Learners should have enough English speaking ability in order to communicate easily and effectively with other people.

Speaking is addressed as one of the dominant skills to be acquired in L2 acquisition (Leong & Ahmadi, 2017; Sabina, 2018) as it is the means of communicating meaningful and comprehensive ideas to listeners (Ho et al., 2020). This is particularly true in educational contexts where students are supposed to utilize a range of speaking skills to participate in both inside and outside classroom conversations with their peers and teachers. When a learner uses spoken words to express something, he/she is going through an interactive process from receiving knowledge, and processing it to conveying meanings and absorbing it. This oral form of communication is a combination of saying words, then making meaningful sentences in requesting, questioning, answering, and conveying meanings. Another claim is that speaking is an appropriate selection of vocabulary to make speaking patterns with correct grammar use, which illustrates

communicative purposes (Contreras Ospitia et al., 2016).

In the light of reports on the sophistication of speaking skills, it is conceivable that learners in the EFL contexts have trouble acquiring oral skills because of a shortage of speaking practice beyond the classroom context. According to Rao (2019), EFL students face difficulties in speaking grammatical sentences is a popular challenge for EFL learners worldwide.

In Hong Kong, one study conducted to clarify the understanding of L2 speaking problems consolidates that students' speaking problems could be derived from three academic terms including sociocultural, institutional, and interpersonal contexts (Gan, 2012). In addition, lacking inside and outside classroom interaction opportunities together with insufficient investments in language curriculum could also add up to students' speaking problems.

Efrizal (2016) expressed that speaking is of great significance for people's interaction where they speak everywhere and every day. Speaking is the way of communicating ideas and messages orally. If we want to encourage students to communicate in English, we should use the language in real communication and ask them to do the same process.

The significance of speaking is indicated with the integration of the other language skills. Speaking helps learners develop their vocabulary and grammar skills and then better their writing skills. Students can express their emotions and ideas; say stories; request; talk, discuss and show the various functions of language. Speaking is of vital importance outside the classroom. Therefore, language speakers have more opportunities to find jobs in different organizations and companies. These statements have been supported by Lukas (2017) who said that learners who speak English very well can have a greater chance of better education, finding good jobs, and getting promotions.

In one study, Leong and Ahmadi (2017) also conclude that Malaysian students even challenge themselves with speaking skills in terms of expressing themselves in L2 spoken language. In

another context, EFL Indonesian students have trouble with language barriers, psychological factors including anxiety and motivation, and lack of communicative opportunities and practice (Abrar et al., 2018). It can be seen that second language oral production has always been a great challenge for EFL students in different countries, and Vietnamese EFL learners are no exception. In a recent study conducted in English classrooms in Hanoi, Hoa and Thao (2020) point out that Vietnamese English learners are often inactive in class due to a lack of proper investments in fostering and reinforcing speaking skills.

Speaking problems are also discovered in another high school context in which the students reported that they have no motivation and confidence to produce spoken language because of their limited speaking topic knowledge and listening strategies as well as inappropriate feedback from teachers (Tuan & Mai, 2015). Likewise, with some certain challenges in Vietnamese higher education, Vietnamese university students are usually associated with fear of mistakes, a shortage of lexical items, and a lack of confidence (Ho et al., 2020).

Troubles with communicating in a second language are also reported in a study done at Can Tho University, Mekong Delta region (Quyen et al., 2018). Both teachers and students encounter a range of internal and external factors that hinder their teaching and learning, especially a shortage of after-school activities and speaking environments.

In short, low motivation, disengagement from speaking activities and lack of opportunities to practice speaking are common problems of L2 learners. These problems can be derived from several reasons; nevertheless, it has been commonly proven from a variety of studies in Viet Nam that insufficient speaking practice investments could demotivate students in learning and acquiring speaking skills.

Concerning recommendations in previous studies, promoting students' motivation and creating more collaborative learning activities could develop speaking skills and reduce

difficulties that students are facing (Boonkit, 2012). Furthermore, the employment of diverse technological tools as well as multimedia resources was found to have positive impacts on teachers' teaching practice and assist students' oral language production (Gómez, 2019; Quyen et al., 2018; Sabina, 2018).

In Malaysia, Murugaiah (2016) used the Pecha Kucha (PK) presentation format to enhance oral presentation skills in L2 students at Universiti Sains Malaysia. Thirty distant students worked in groups and completed a task-based activity using the PK format in which the students used twenty slides containing visuals with minimal text presented in twenty seconds. Interview reports and the researcher's observations showed that the PK format is effective in supporting collaborative learning and fostering oral presentation skills in L2, but it posed challenges to students with low proficiency levels. To maximize the benefits of PK, the researcher suggested the inclusion of more pedagogical support and training.

To develop learners' oral communication skills in EFL, Castillo (2016) used the virtual world of Second Life and a distance learning course platform. The researcher found that the virtual world of Second Life played a significant role in improving adult learners' listening and speaking skills. Although some online course platforms are enriched with interactive multimedia tools and dynamic content to facilitating learning, these tools imposed some challenges for learners who lacked digital skills and who were not familiar with the platform. The researcher concluded that the utilization of different web-based technologies in language learning can be a useful strategy in enhancing students' engagement, and teaching practices, and complementing the interactive aspects of these tools Castillo (2016).

In Australia, distance students enrolled in a university preparatory program chose a topic, set an audience, gave an oral presentation, and reflected on their experience. The students' responses via portfolio reflections and interviews indicated that this activity fulfilled their needs and that oral presentations were a

meaningful and transformative experience McDougall and Holden (2017).

In a study by Galindo et al. (2020), engineering students individually created a video in which they explained the solution to one of their homework assignments. Following the video production, the students received feedback using an assessment rubric. Then, they produced a second version of the video for which they were assessed for the overall mark. The findings of the study showed that this activity helped the students improve their ability to give oral presentations.

Further studies in the literature focused on how some specific speaking skills are developed in DL. For example, Martin (2020) examined how distance language learners' pronunciation skills develop with and without targeted pronunciation training during the first semester of language instruction at the university. For that purpose, the researcher designed a computer-assisted method of pronunciation instruction and tried it for one semester with a sample of 67 distance students learning German as L2 online. The results showed that distance students who received targeted pronunciation training improved significantly and outperformed students in the control group who did not receive such training on measures of perception and production accuracy.

The research study conducted by Sevy-Biloon and Chroman (2019) used video chat applications to improve the English language fluency of students in Ecuador in a teacher preparation program for English as a Foreign Language teachers. To fill the deficit of EFL teachers in Ecuador, the Universidad Nacional de Educacion (UNAE) created a new major for EFL teachers; however, the students within this program had little to no exposure to English. Sevy-Biloon and Chroman (2019) sought to investigate if the use of digital applications would increase student intrinsic motivation while also improving oral communication in the target language, English. The research study is a mixed methods approach and tracked seventeen participants in this five-week program.

Sevy-Biloon and Chroman (2019) created a video chat experience for students to practice English through the digital mediums of WhatsApp, Skype, Facebook, or Facetime with university students in the United States. Sevy-Biloon and Chroman (2019) also utilized authentic tasks to increase motivation while improving oral communication. Through pre and post-questionnaires, monitoring of meeting minutes, and oral pre-tests and post-tests, the researchers concluded that students were more intrinsically motivated to participate and increase communicative fluency through the use of the authentic medium of video chats. While only two students of the seventeen students did not complete the activity fully due to internet issues and conflicts with schedules, the majority of the participants reported positive results using a digital medium to improve fluency. As reported through the post questionnaire, participants stated that the digital application of video chats helped them in developing positive experiences with native English speakers, increased motivation, and improved their oral English communication skills. The post-test results also reported that the participants improved their overall oral communication skills in English. Several participants were intrinsically motivated to continue the video chats with their United States peers after the completion of the program.

In another study, Ahmad (2016) employed a mixed methods approach to investigate the effectiveness of Technology Assisted Language Learning (TALL) on language development and student motivation as opposed to the traditional methods of EFL instruction. The twenty-five Saudi participants placed in an intensive English program completed tasks focused on listening, reading, and speaking. The two groups, a controlled group using traditional and non-TALL methods and the primarily TALL method-oriented group, confirmed that the students used a variety of digital applications, such as matching words with pictures, listening to native English speakers through CD-ROMs, and using translation digital sources outperformed the traditional methods group significantly in each test (Ahmad, 2016).

Participants displayed increased motivation using digital applications. Students were assessed on each domain, and it was reported that students using the TALL approach were more adept at understanding the speaking and intonations of native speakers than those using the non-traditional method. The TALL experimental group was intrinsically motivated to take full advantage of the digital sources in their English language development which led to high performances on the four tests implemented throughout the research study. While Ahmad (2016) did not explicitly explain the EFL instruction for the non-experimental group, the research study reiterates the resounding belief from past studies that digital platforms increase student intrinsic motivation in the acquisition, fluency, and development of participants' second language.

The literature and studies helped the research in the conceptualization of the study. Specifically, the various studies and literature assisted and guided the research in determining the different variables and methods in the conduct of the present study.

Methodology

The research utilized the Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest group design. Two intact heterogeneous classes were used in the conduct of the study. The experimental group (40 students) was exposed to video-recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid, and the control group (40 students) was exposed to conventional speaking tasks using Google Meet.

Instruments of the Study

The researcher adapted the speaking module of IELTS, modified as a pretest and posttest, as a data-gathering tool of the study to gauge the level of oral performance of both the experimental and control groups. A series of speaking tasks supported the instrument. Eighty students participated in the conduct of the study.

As for the rating scale used for the assessment of the students' oral performances, the public version of the IELTS speaking scale was

adopted. As the main focus of the study is to investigate the impact of Flipgrid on learners' speaking ability, the criterion of (a) Fluency and Coherence in the IELTS scale was divided into two separate criteria as (a) Fluency and (b) Content Development.

The researcher used the mean, standard deviation, and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to treat data.

Procedure

The research employed pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design which was conducted in three stages. In the pre-stage, before the intervention, both experimental and control groups were given a speaking pretest to measure the level of their oral performance. In the while-stage, primarily based on the English 10's curriculum, speaking tasks were equally delivered to students in both groups during one grading period.

For the experimental group, students were tasked to record four oral presentation videos using Flipgrid. For the control group, the students were asked to deliver four live oral presentations to the class through Google Meet. The teachers and the classmates provided feedback after each performance. One week was allocated for the students to accomplish one speaking task, hence the data collection procedure for this study took approximately eight weeks.

Results and Discussion

This study primarily sought to determine how the video recording platform (Flipgrid) affects the oral performance of English as a Second Language Grade 10 students of Liceo de Cagayan University Junior High School.

Table 1. Level of Oral Performance of Students Exposed to Conventional English Speaking Tasks Using Google Meet During the Pretest and Posttest

Band	Range	Pretest				Posttest			
		f	Mean	SD	Interpretation	f	Mean	SD	Interpretation
9	8.50 – 9.00	0	3.35	1.25	Extremely Limited User	1	4.60	1.60	Moderate User
8	7.50 – 8.49	1				0			
7	6.50 – 7.49	0				4			
6	5.50 – 6.49	1				5			
5	4.50 – 5.49	3				11			
4	3.50 – 4.49	10				9			
3	2.50 - 3.49	15				6			
2	1.50 – 2.49	10				4			
1	0 - 1.49	0				0			
	TOTAL	40							

Legend:

Band	Range	Interpretation
9	8.50 – 9.00	Expert User
8	7.50 – 8.49	Very Good User
7	6.50 – 7.49	Good User
6	5.50 – 6.49	Competent User
5	4.50 – 5.49	Moderate User
4	3.50 – 4.49	Limited User
3	2.50 - 3.49	Extremely Limited User
2	1.50 – 2.49	Intermittent User
1	0 - 1.49	Non-User

Table 1 reveals that the level of oral performance of the control group before and after exposure

to conventional English-speaking tasks using Google Meet showed a significant increase.

Before exposure to the conventional speaking tasks, the control group's oral performance was classified as "Extremely Limited Users" with a mean of 3.35 (1.25). According to IELTS's scoring band interpretation, this demonstrates that at this level, their fundamental communication skills are restricted to familiar contexts and that they cannot employ sophisticated language, which causes issues with comprehension and expression.

After exposure to the conventional speaking tasks, the control group's mean score was 4.60 (1.60), indicating that their oral performance is categorized as a "Moderate User." Based on IELTS's scoring band interpretation, this result indicates that students have a limited grasp of the language and can handle simple interpersonal interactions. More so, this implies that students

obtained higher oral performance after exposure to conventional English-speaking tasks using Google Meet.

These findings show that the posttest mean score, 4.60 (1.60), was higher than the pretest mean score, 3.35 (1.25). This implies that students improve their oral performance after being exposed to speaking tasks. According to Morozova (2013), speaking tasks are effective methods for ESL learners to develop their oral performance. This is an effective strategy that teachers can incorporate into their English classes that will benefit students, especially those with low oral performance. More so, Harmer (2012) noted that because of students' limited speaking opportunities, exposing them to speaking tasks will bolster their speaking skills.

Table 2. Level of Oral Performance of Students Exposed to Video-Recording English Speaking Tasks Using Flipgrid During the Pretest and Posttest

Band	Range	Pretest				Posttest			
		f	Mean	SD	Interpretation	f	Mean	SD	Interpretation
9	8.50 – 9.00	0	5.10	1.08	Moderate User	0	6.28	1	Competent User
8	7.50 – 8.49	1				1			
7	6.50 – 7.49	2				2			
6	5.50 – 6.49	8				8			
5	4.50 – 5.49	22				22			
4	3.50 – 4.49	4				4			
3	2.50 - 3.49	2				2			
2	1.50 – 2.49	1				1			
1	0 - 1.49	0				0			
	TOTAL	40				40			

Legend:

Band	Range	Interpretation
9	8.50 – 9.00	Expert User
8	7.50 – 8.49	Very Good User
7	6.50 – 7.49	Good User
6	5.50 – 6.49	Competent User
5	4.50 – 5.49	Moderate User
4	3.50 – 4.49	Limited User
3	2.50 - 3.49	Extremely Limited User
2	1.50 – 2.49	Intermittent User
1	0 - 1.49	Non-User

Table 2 presents the students' oral performance level before and after exposure to video recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid. During the pretest, results show that the experimental group's oral performance level was categorized

as "Moderate User" with a mean of 5.10 (1.08). According to IELTS's scoring band interpretation, this demonstrates that, at this level, individuals are proficient in the language and can use and comprehend rather complicated

language, especially in unfamiliar contexts. This result is supported by Efrizal (2016), who expressed that students' oral performance is of great significance for people interaction.

After the posttest, the mean score obtained by the students is 6.28 (1.281), which indicates that their oral performance is classified as "Competent User." This shows that they have developed operational command of the language

and an understanding of detailed reasoning and complex language. This implies that the students obtained a higher level of performance after the intervention was employed.

This result shows that after being exposed to video-recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid, students' speaking anxiety decreased, resulting in a higher performance during the posttest (Tuyet & Khang, 2020).

Table 3. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for the Significant Difference in the Oral Performances of the Students Exposed to Conventional Speaking Tasks and Flipgrid

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Corrected Model	192.197a	2	96.099	269.172	.000	
Intercept	2.467	1	2.467	6.911	.010	
Pretest Score	136.085	1	136.085	381.174	.000	Significant
Group	1.54	1	1.154	3.232	.076	Not significant
Error	27.490	77	.357			
Total	2585.000	80				
Corrected Total	219.688	79				

Note: a. - R Squared = .875 (Adjusted R Squared = .872); Cohen's Effect Guidelines; 0.2 – small effect; 0.5 – moderate effect; 0.8 – large effect.

Table 3 presents the Univariate Analysis of Variance (ANCOVA) for the significant difference in the students exposed to Flipgrid's oral performance. Based on the study's findings, as shown in the Table, the computed p-value (0.076) of the pretest is lesser than the significance standard set in the study at 0.05. This reveals a statistically significant difference in the oral performance of ESL students exposed to Flipgrid and conventional English-speaking tasks.

Both test scores show that the posttest scores are higher than the pretest scores. This confirms that integrating both the conventional speaking tasks using Google Meet and video-recording speaking tasks using Flipgrid are effective strategies for improving student's oral performance in English class.

These results support the claims of Zaenal (2020) and Juniartini (2020), and Mango (2021) about the effectiveness of Google Met and Flipgrid. Based on the study of Zaenal (2020) and Juniartini (2020), speaking tasks using

Google Meet are good strategies to develop students' oral performance. On the other hand, Mango (2021) claimed that Flipgrid helps students develop their oral and listening skills and confidence in public speaking. More so, Mango (2021) added that Flipgrid can be used as a learning approach to make student learning outcomes effective.

Conclusions

The posttest results of the control group show that exposure to conventional speaking tasks using Google Meet can significantly improve ESL students' oral performance. This supports the claims of Zaenal (2020) and Juniartini (2020).

The posttest results of the experimental group show that integration of Flipgrid in the speaking tasks of ESL students can significantly improve their oral performance. This supplements the study of Mango (2021) that Flipgrid help students develop their oral and listening skills and confidence in public speaking.

Both experimental and control groups exposed to conventional speaking tasks and Flipgrid show an increase in their oral performance after the posttest. This statistically shows that both are effective when it comes to improving students' oral performance. This can be concluded that Flipgrid can be used as an assessment tool to help teachers improve students' oral language performance.

References

- Afrianto, D. (2016). *Using Google Hangouts for teaching English online*. Proceedings of the fourth international seminar on English language and teaching, 4, 80-94.
- Adnan, M., & Anwar, K. (2020). Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Students' perspectives. *Journal of Pedagogical Sociology and Psychology*, 2(1). <http://doi.org/10.33902/JPSP.2020261309>
- Agan, T., Anderson, D., Atwood, A., Casarez, L., Heron, A., & Self, R. (2019). Flipgrid to enhance communication in distance education. *The Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin*, 85(4), 35–37.
- Ahmad, J. (2016). Technology-assisted language learning is a silver bullet for enhancing language competence and performance: A Case Study. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 7, 118. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijalel.v.5n.7p.118>
- Al-Jarf, R. (2021). *Investigating equity in distance learning in Saudi Arabia during the Covid-19 Pandemic*. The 17th International Scientific Conference e-Learning and Software for Education. Bucharest, Romania.
- Al-Khasawneh, F.M. (2016). Investigating foreign language learning anxiety: a case of Saudi undergraduate EFL learners. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 12(1), 137–148.
- Amirulloh, D. N., Damayanti, I. L., & Citraningrum, E. (2020). Flipgrid: A Pathway to Enhance Students' Speaking Performance. *Atlantis Express*, 546, 90-91. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210427.014>
- Benson, S. D. (2015). Task-based language teaching: An empirical study of task transfer. *Language Teaching Research*, 20, 341–365. <http://doi.org/10.1177/1362168815569829>
- Boonkit, K. (2012). Enhancing the development of speaking skills for non-native speakers of English. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 1305–1309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.191>
- Bordoloi, R. Das, P., & Das, K. (2021). Perception towards online/blended learning during the Covid-19 pandemic: academic analytics in the Indian context. *Asian Association of Open Universities Journal*, 16(1), 41-60. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAOUJ-09-2020-0079>.
- Castillo, M. I. (2016). *Using a virtual world as a communication space to supplement an online course platform for teaching oral communication skills to adult English as a second language learners*. Ed.D. Dissertation, Texas A & M University – Kingsville. ERIC ED596393.
- Chandra, Y. (2020). Online education during COVID-19: perception of academic stress and emotional intelligence coping strategies among college students. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 10(2), 229-238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-05-2020-0097>.
- Chinaza, S.I. (2021). Google Meet as a synchronous language learning tool for emergency online distant learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: Perceptions of language instructors and preservice teachers. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 2, 640-659. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2.5.163.12>
- Cooke, S. D. (2013). Examining transcription, autonomy and reflective practice in language development. *RELC Journal*, 44(1), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688212473271>
- David, A.T. (2018). Synchronous Learning Vs. Asynchronous Learning in Online Education. Retrieved from <http://thebestschools.org/magazines/synchronous-vs.asynchronous-education/>
- Duong, T.M., Nguyen, H.T.T. (2021). Implementing task-based language teaching in

- Vietnamese secondary schools: What hinders EFL teachers? *TESL-EJ*, 25, 1–15.
- Efrizal, D. (2012). Improving Students' Speaking through Communicative Language Teaching Method at Mts Ja-alhaq, Senator Ali Basa Islamic Boarding School of Bengkulu, Indonesia. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(20), 127–134.
- Emon, A. K., Alif, A. R., & Islam, M. S. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on the Institutional Education. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 11(2), 34–46. <https://doi.org/10.9734/AJESS//v11i230288>
- English First (2016). *EF English Proficiency Index*. Lucerne, Switzerland: Education First Ltd.
- Forsythe, E., & Raine, P. (2019). Bring the back-row students to the front of the class with Flipgrid. *The Language Teacher*, 43(4), 22–24. <https://doi.org/10.37546/JALTTLT43.4>
- Galindo, C., Gregori, P., Martínez, V. (2020). Using videos to improve oral presentation skills in distance learning engineering master's degrees. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(1), 103–114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1662118>
- Gan, Z. (2012). Understanding L2 speaking problems: Implications for ESL curriculum development in a teacher training institution in Hong Kong. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 37(1), 43–59. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2012v37n1.4>
- Gómez, J. C. (2019). *Multimedia resources and their incidence in the English speaking skill in students of tenth grade EGB at UE Maria Andrea, the school year 2019-2020*. Bachelor's degree, Universidad Laica Vicente Rocafuerte.
- Hammoodi, S., & Alishah, A. (2020). The evolvement of autonomous learning through social constructivist movement. *Egitim Fakultes Dergisi*, 6, 91-105. <https://doi.org/10.17932/IAU.EFD.2015.013/>
- Harmer, J. (2012). *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. China: Pearson.
- Harris, A. (2020). COVID-19 – school leadership in crisis? *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 5(3/4), 321–326. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPCC-06-2020-0045>
- Ho, P. V. P., Thien, N. M., An, N.T.M., & Vy, N. N. H. (2020). The effects of using games on EFL students' speaking performances. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 10(1), 183-193. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v10n1p183>
- Huber, S. G. & Helm, C. (2020). COVID-19 and schooling: evaluation, assessment, and accountability in times of crises— reacting quickly to explore key issues for policy, practice, and research with the school barometer. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation, and Accountability*, 32, 237–270. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-020-09322-y>
- Innes, A. (2020). Student evaluation of Flipgrid at a Japanese university: Embarrassment and connection. *Maria Curie-Sklodowska University Press*, 44(3), 151-166. <https://doi.org/10.17951/lsmll.2020.44.3.151-166>
- Johnson, M., & Skarphol, M. (2018). *The effects of digital portfolios and Flipgrid on student engagement and communication in a connected learning secondary visual arts classroom*. Master's thesis, St. Catherine University.
- Lamb, M. (2015). The Motivation Dimension of Language Teaching. *Language Teaching*, 50(3). 301-346. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000088>
- Lander, G. (2014). 10 tips on how to use Google plus hangouts. Retrieved from <http://www.jeffbullas.com/2013/12/04/10tips-on-how-to-use-Google-plus-hangouts/>
- Leong, L. & Ahmadi, S. M. (2017). An analysis of factors influencing learners' English speaking skills. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 2(1), 34-41. <https://doi.org/10.18869/acadpub.ijree.2.1.34>
- Liu, M. (2013). Blended learning in a university EFL writing course: description and evaluation. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 4(2), 301. <https://doi.org/10.4304/jltr.4.2.301-309>

- Kondal, B. & Durga Prasad, V. (2020). Effectiveness of Video Recording towards Developing Speaking Skills. *Waffen-und Kostumkunde Journal*, 11(9), 42-47
- Kurose, M. (2019). Becoming a more active and creative language learner with digital tools. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=ED594862&site=eds-live>
- Lewandowski, M. (2015). Creating virtual classrooms (using Google Hangouts) to improve language competency. *Language Issues: The ESOL Journal*, 26(1), 37-42.
- Lorente, L. M., Arrabal, A. A., & Pulido-Montes, C. (2020). The Right to Education and ICT during COVID-19: An International Perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9091. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219091>
- Lowenthal, P. R., & Moore, R. L. (2020). Exploring student perceptions of Flipgrid in online courses. *Online Learning Journal*, 24(4), 28-41. <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v24i4.2335>
- Lucanus, A. (2017). Oral Communication Skills Are Important for Students. Stanford University. Retrieved from <https://collegepuzzle.stanford.edu/oral-communication-skills-are-important-for-students/>
- Martin, I. (2020). Pronunciation development and instruction in distance language learning. *Language Learning & Technology*, 24(1), 86–106. <https://doi.org/10.125/44711>
- Melisa, S. (2020). The impact of effective planning on the teaching and learning process. Retrieved from <http://www.projecttopics.org/the-impact-of-effective-planning-on-teaching-and-learning-process>
- McDougall, J. & Holden, H. (2017). The silence about oral presentation skills in the distance and online education: new perspectives from an Australian university preparatory program. *Open Learning*, 32(2), 163–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2017.1316187>
- McLain, T. R. (2018). Integration of the video response app Flipgrid in the business writing classroom. *International Journal of Educational Technology and Learning*, 4(2), 68–75. <https://doi.org/10.20448/2003.42.68.75>
- Mennim, P. (2012). Learner negotiation of L2 form in transcription exercises. *ELT Journal*, 66(1), 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccr018>
- Merrill, J. (2018). Flipgrid- A Social Learning Platform. Retrieved from <https://www.thetechteacher.net/2018/07/flipgrid-social-learningplatform.html>
- Miller, S. C., McIntyre, C. J., & Lindt, S. F. (2020). Engaging technology in elementary school: Flipgrid's potential. *Childhood Education*, 96(3), 62–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00094056.2020.1766677>
- Mishra, L., Gupta, T., & Shree, A. (2020). Online teaching-learning in higher education during the lockdown period of the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.100012>
- Moore, M.G., & Kearsley, G. (2012). *Distance Education: A System View*, 3rd ed. Belmont, Calif: Wadsworth.
- Morozova, Y. (2013). Methods of Enhancing Speaking Skills of Elementary Level Students. *Translation Journal*, 17(1).
- Murugaiah, P. (2016). Pecha Kucha style Powerpoint presentation: an innovative call approach to developing oral presentation skills of tertiary students. *Teaching English with Technology*, 16(1), 88-104.
- Nur, B., & Jafre, M. (2012). The Use of Video in ESL Teaching and Learning: YouTube Potential as a Resource. *Diges Pendidik*, 2, 94-104.
- Nursat, M. (2021). Educational Response toward COVID-19 Pandemic: Perception, Problem, and Prospects A Bangladeshi Context. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 2(5), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2021.2.5.163>

- Park, M. (2015). Implementing computer-assisted task-based language teaching in the Korean secondary EFL context. In Shehadeh, A. & Coombe, C.A. (Eds.), *Task-based Language Teaching in Foreign Language Contexts: Research and Implementation* (pp. 215-240). <https://doi.org/10.1075/tblt.4.14par>
- Paulina, B. F. (2017). *Improving the Students' Speaking Competence Using Screencast-O-Matic*. Ed.D. Dissertation, Sanata Dharma University.156332011.
- Pierce, D. (2017). What Effective Blended Learning Looks Like. The Journal. Retrieved from <https://thejournal.com/articles/2017/01/11/what-effective-blended-learning-looks-like.aspx>
- Pittman, J. S. T. (2021). An action research case study: digital equity and educational inclusion during an emergent COVID-19 divide. *Journal for Multicultural Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JME-09-2020-0099>
- Pop, A., Tomuletiu, E. A., & David, D. (2012). EFL speaking communication with asynchronous voice tools for adult students. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 1199-1203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.262>
- Quyen, V. P., Nga, P. T. M., & Nguyen, H. T. (2018). Challenges to speaking skills encountered by English-majored students: A story of one Vietnamese university in the Mekong Delta. *Can Tho University Journal of Science*, 54(5), 38-44. <https://doi.org/10.22144/ctu.jcn.2018.022>
- Rao, P. S. (2019). The importance of speaking skills in English classrooms. *Alford Council of International English & Literature Journal (ACIELJ)*, 2(2), 1-12.
- Sabina, Z. (2018). The importance of teaching listening and speaking skills. *World Science*, 7(34), 52-55. https://doi.org/10.31435/rsglobal_ws/12062018/5881
- Salvador, R. (2018). The trolley problem: a social constructivist pedagogy approach. *The Journal of Education for Business*, 94, 333-341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08832323.2018.1327749>
- Sevy-Biloon, J., & Chroman, T. (2019). Authentic use of technology to improve EFL communication and motivation through international language exchange video chat. *Teaching English with Technology*, 19(2), 44-58.
- Shehzadi, S., Nisar, Q. A., Hussain, M. S., Basheer, M. F., Hameed, W. U., & Chaudhry, N. I. (2020). The role of digital learning toward students' satisfaction and university brand image at educational institutes of Pakistan: a post-effect of COVID-19. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 10(2), 276-294, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-04--0063>
- Statt, N. (2017). Google's second Allo Messaging bot is an AI-driven GIF generator. Retrieved from <http://www.theverge.com/1/25/14393380/googleallomessagingbot-luckygiftgenerator>
- Stoszkowski, J., Hodgkinson, A., & Collins, D. (2020). Using Flipgrid to improve reflection: A collaborative online approach to coaching development. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 26(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2020.1789575>
- Syahrizal, T., & Pamungkas, M. Y. (2020). Revealing Students' Responds on the Use of Flipgrid in Speaking Class: Survey on ICT. *Acuity: Journal of English Language Pedagogy, Literature, and Culture*, 98-107. <https://doi.org/10.35974/acuity.v6i2.2459>
- Tan, C. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on student motivation, community of inquiry, and learning performance. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 10(2), 308-321. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-05-2020-0084>
- Tan, E. H. (2019). *Bring the Back-row Students to the Front of the Class with Flipgrid*. JALT Praxis: TLT Wired, pp. 22-24.
- Thomson, C. J. (2017). Coronavirus and challenging times for education in developing countries. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/education-plus-development/2020/04/13/coronavirus-and->

[challenging-times-for-education-in-developing-countries/](#)

Tinsley, T. & Board, K. (2013). Languages for the Future, The British Council, London, UK. Retrieved from <https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/languages-for-the-future-report-v3.pdf>.

Topacio, K. N. M. (2018). Exploring the use of online educational platforms in teaching writing among ESL students. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 14(1), 86-101.

Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), ep2001. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdll/8311>

Tuan, N. H., & Mai, T. N. (2015). Factors affecting students' speaking performance at Le Thanh Hien high school. *Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 3(2), 8-23.

Wei, J., Chen, J. C., & Adawu, A. (2014). Teaching ESL beginners metacognitive writing strategies through multimedia software. *CATESOL Journal*, 26(1), 60-75.

Widiyawati, W. (2014). *Improving Speaking Through Telling Past Experiences*. Indraprasta University Jakarta

Zheng, X. and Borg, S. (2013). Task-based learning and teaching in China: Secondary school teachers' beliefs and practices. *Language Teaching Research*, 18, 205–221. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168813505941>